

Pharisees

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Entry tags: Jewish Traditions, Abrahamic, Religious Group

The Pharisees are an early Jewish sect dating from the late Hellenistic period to the end of the first century CE. Our primary evidence for this group derives from the Jewish historian Josephus (d. ca 100 CE), early Christian literature, and the later Tannaitic literature. According to Josephus (War 2.8; Ant. 13.5.9; 13.10.6; 18.1.2-6), the Pharisees are one of three "philosophical sects" of the Jews, who "are friendly to one another, and are for the exercise of concord, and regard for the public" (War 2.8.14; trans. Whiston). The group appears to have formed sometime during the Hasmonean period (ca. 140 BCE) as an influential party among a majority of the Jewish people. As a political entity, they appear to have gained popularity in response to the Sadducees and the Hasmonean High Priest John Hyrcanus, securing political leverage under Salome Alexandra. The Gospel sources offer a polemical portrayal of the Pharisees at odds with the early Jesus movement (Matthew 23:1-39), often engaging in ritualistic dispute with Jesus and his disciples (Mark 7:1-23). In other early Christian sources, the apostle Paul identifies himself with the Pharisees (Acts 22:3; 23:6; Philippians 3:5; Galatians 1:14), and elsewhere, is depicted as actively persecuting members of the early Jesus movement (Acts 8:1-3). In these sources, a positive portrayal of the Pharisees may be found in the figure of Gamaliel (Acts 5:34-42), who persuades the Sanhedrin to show mercy to followers of Jesus. The term Pharisee may derive from the Hebrew word "to separate" (*perushim*); however, this etymology has been recently questioned (Rivkin, "Who Were the Pharisees?"). The sectarian boundaries of the Pharisees were determined by a commitment to food and purity rituals laid out in Oral (e.g., "tradition of the fathers") and Written (e.g., the Torah) traditions. Their belief system consists of monotheism, an afterlife (of both reward and punishment), the immortality of the soul (especially in contrast to the Sadducees), and resurrection for the righteous. In the literary evidence, Pharisees are often characterized as the leading experts in interpreting the law and, according to Josephus, less stringent in rendering punitive judgement than the Sadducees.

Date Range: 150 BCE - 70 CE

Region: Roman Palestine

Region tags: Israel, State of Palestine, Middle East

Roman Palestine

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Ellis Rivkin, "Who Were the Pharisees?" in *Judaism in Late Antiquity* (ed. Alan J. Avery-Peck and Jacob Neusner; Part Three. *Where We Stand: Issues and Debates in Ancient Judaism*. Vol 3; Leiden: Brill:2000), 1-33.
- Source 2: Jacob Neusner, *From Politics to Piety: The Emergence of Pharisaic Judaism*. 2nd ed. New York: Ktav Pub. House, 1979.
- Source 3: Jacob Neusner and Bruce Chilton eds, *In Quest of the Historical Pharisees*, Waco: Baylor

University Press, 2007.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bibleodyssey.org/en/people/main-articles/pharisees>
- Source 1 Description: An excellent online database powered by the Society of Biblical Literature. This article is written by Professor Joshua Garroway of Hebrew Union College.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.oxfordbiblicalstudies.com/article/opr/t94/e1462>
- Source 2 Description: Another dictionary style entry containing quality information.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: https://www.sefaria.org/Mishnah_Chagigah.2?lang=bi
- Source 1 Description: See especially the Mishnah Hagigah 2:7.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/searchresults?q=Josephus>
- Source 2 Description: A link to Josephus' writings in Greek and English online at Perseus.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/online-bibles/novum-testamentum-graece-na-28/read-the-bible-text/>
- Source 3 Description: A link to the New Testament with relevant Greek and English options. (See, for example, Matthew 23:1-39).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: According to our primary sources, and depending the source one reads, the Pharisees are in dispute with the Hasmoneans, the Sadducees, and members of the early Jesus

movement. While they would have been in contact with Greco-Roman culture, the primary evidence is interested in intrareligious differences.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Pharisees profess an immortality of the soul that seems to be at home in other Greco-Roman philosophical sects. The nature of our sources is biased, and for this reason contact with Pharisaic Judaism is presented as hostile (see Matthew chapter 23). However, and importantly, the contact is of an intrareligious type within Judaism. The Pharisees seem to have been well received among a majority of the common people. Josephus compares the Pharisees with the Stoics, which may suggest a degree of accommodation.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees lived in and among Roman Palestine (not separatist like Qumranites). Josephus's bias suggested an interest in offering greater appeal for Judaism, including the Pharisees. One could argue that Pharisees appear more neutral than their counterparts, the Sadducees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Our sources do not depict Pharisees at odds with other Pharisees in a violent nature.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees seem to disappear following the destruction of the Temple (ca. 70 CE) at the hands of the Romans. There is also apparent conflict, though not necessarily violent conflict, with the Hasmoneans in the middle of the second century BCE. The presentation of the Pharisees within New Testament sources appears occasionally violent in nature. The figure of Paul, for example, is presented as a Pharisee and one who persecutes Christians (Acts 8:1-3). Josephus, on the other hand, provides us with a different picture: as one who identifies with

the "sect of the Pharisees" (Life 3), he presents them as a more lenient group (Gamaliel in Acts 5 confirms this).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: According to Josephus (Vita/Life), it appears that one had the choice to study with the "rules of the sect" of the Pharisees (he does so at age 19). In this passage, he compares them to the Stoics. Elsewhere, Josephus refers to them as a philosophy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by class:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The data is unclear. It would appear that a certain level of socioeconomic status is beneficial for one's ability to study with Pharisees (e.g., Josephus is 19, educated with higher class/status). However, their appeal to the Jewish populace suggests broad accessibility.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: In his autobiography, Josephus is 19 when he goes to study with Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

Notes: Our sources depict Pharisees as male, but do show female interest with their group (Josephus Ant. 17.41-43)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: The scholastic nature of Josephus's encounter with the Pharisees suggest one studies with them. There are no baptism rituals, for example, as we see among Jewish baptizing groups (e.g., John or Bannus). As a Jewish sect, adherents would have undergone the process of circumcision at birth.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: How does one become a Pharisee? It appears, in the case of Josephus, that one may study with them. In the case of John Hyrcanus's friend Jonathan, Josephus reports that Hyrcanus forced him to "leave the party of the Pharisees" (Ant. 13.10.6). This story is unclear, but perhaps suggests one could also voluntarily leave the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The act of proselytizing is possible. There are Jewish proselytizers in antiquity, but sources are unclear if this is a particular identity of the Pharisee sect. Their popularity may have attracted students voluntarily to their sect to study.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: Scholars dispute the nature of the Pharisaic movement (as a political entity or a philosophical sect). In regard to its political identity, see Tcherikover, *Hellenistic Civilization and the Jews* (Philadelphia: Jewish Publication Society of America, 1959), 254-56. It is clear from Josephus that the Pharisees stand opposed to the Sadducees and John Hyrcanus (Hyrcanus's friend Jonathan purportedly leaves the Pharisees in Ant. 13.10.5-6). Lastly, Josephus presents the Pharisees as having political influence over Salome Alexandra, during which time they may have had a degree of political oversight and influence.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: At different times in their history, the Sadducees and the Pharisees garnered political support from the ruling party. If the priests at the Temple received political funding, it is unclear. While the affair does not involve the Pharisees, it is worth noting that the Temple treasury is a point of dispute in the Gospel of Mark (12:41-44).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: This is a feature shared by Judaisms of the time period. During the Second Temple period, Herod the Great expanded and rebuilt the Temple.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– Yes

Notes: This is not specific to the Pharisees per se. During the Hasmonean period, the role of the High Priest was multi-faceted, functioning as both political head of people (or "king") and "high priest," thus conflating these categories. Under Roman rule, the political title appears to shift to "ethnarch" and High Priest. In any case, the High Priest would have been perceived as ordained by God. Our sources indicate the Sanhedrin (or gerousia) functioned as a governing body of elders.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: This is not particular to the Pharisees. It also depends on what period to which we refer. Under Roman rule, Judea becomes a Roman province, and it appears as if political autonomy for early Judaism has run its course. Prior to this, in Second Temple Judaism, the role of the High Priest would have been understood as both political and religious. There is considerable conflict around the role and function of the High Priest during the time of the Pharisees in the late Hellenistic period.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The evidence is mixed. On the one hand, from the writings of Paul, it is unclear why Paul

receives punishment (2 Corinthians 11:24-35) or who, exactly, punishes him. Additionally, the Pharisees practice certain rituals surrounding food customs, and according to some, eating unconsecrated food would violate cultic boundaries (see Neusner, *From Politics to Piety*). On the other hand, Hyrcanus' friend Jonathan appears to leave the Pharisees with no consequence. This would call into question a traditional understanding of apostasy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no data for the Pharisees in particular. As for early Judaism, extrapolating numbers from this period is fraught with difficulties. One major reason is that our literary sources (e.g., Josephus) tend to exaggerate data and size of populations. Material evidence (e.g., numismatics) would be one way to estimate or cross-reference the data found in the literature; however, the material evidence for the period is scarce. E.P. Sanders estimates "less than one million" for the Jewish population in the first century BCE (*Judaism: Practice and Belief*, 158). Bar Hebraeus, of the thirteenth century, estimates seven million Jews in the Roman empire. Others estimate include 300,000 in the Roman Palestine region. (For the source of these numbers, and more, see Tcherikover, *Hellenistic Civilization and the Jews*, 292-93,504-5). These estimates are difficult to measure with high levels of accuracy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We have no data for the Pharisees in particular. As for early Judaism, extrapolating numbers from this period is fraught with difficulties. One major reason is that our literary sources (e.g., Josephus) tend to exaggerate data and size of populations. Material evidence (e.g., numismatics) would be one way to estimate or cross-reference the data found in the literature; however, the material evidence for the period is scarce. E.P. Sanders estimates "less than one million" for the Jewish population in the first century BCE (*Judaism: Practice and Belief*, 158). Bar Hebraeus, of the thirteenth century, estimates seven million Jews in the Roman empire. Others estimate include 300,000 in the Roman Palestine region. (For the source of these numbers, and more, see Tcherikover, *Hellenistic Civilization and the Jews*, 292-93,504-5). These estimates are difficult to measure with high levels of accuracy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative

and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees were students of the written Torah. Their intensive study and interpretation of Torah was a key feature of their sect.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: A distinctive of the Pharisees were their comment to oral tradition as well as to the written Torah (see "tradition of the elders" in Mark 7:3). According to Josephus, this commitment put them at odds with the Sadducees (Ant. 13.10.6).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Notes: In accordance with other sects of early Judaism, the Torah was revealed by God to Moses.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Revelation is definitively God's, so the Law would be understood likewise. At the same time, angels may mediate divine revelation within the stories of the Hebrew Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Oral tradition ("the tradition of the elders") is inspired by God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Notes: A caveat is necessary here, in that the oral tradition is commonly referred to as "tradition of the elders." It is inspired by God but there is also a dynamic interplay with human beings that is the source of future intra-religious controversies.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: There are open for interpretation however. For the Pharisees, oral tradition ("the tradition of the elders") serves as an inspired guide for following Torah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Torah.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees are traditionally associated with facilitating pious practices among the common people, such as prayer and the reading of Scripture. For this reason, some older scholarship has assigned the creation of early synagogues to Pharisees. However, our sources are unclear if Pharisees "controlled" these religious institutions or to what extent they had a hand in creating them. It seems plausible that the local synagogue would have been a staple feature of Pharisaic Judaism. Our evidence for this relationship may be found in the New Testament (see John 12:42). The Pharisees would have also participated in cultic rituals at the Jerusalem Temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: While early Jews likely buried their dead in family tombs, there is little evidence specific to the Pharisees. A highly polemical comment in Matthew 23:27,29 suggests that Pharisees did secure tombs and graves for to bury their loved ones.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While early Jews likely buried their dead in cemeteries as well (and some evidence to suggest cemeteries were in proximity to synagogues), there is little evidence specific to the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Jerusalem Temple was a central feature of early Judaism. Despite the variety of Judaisms within the first-century, association (either positive or negative) with the Temple was a central facet. For more on the centrality of the Temple to first-century Judaisms, see E. P. Sanders, *Judaism: Practice and Belief 63 BCE - 66 CE* (London: SCM Press, 1992), 47-72.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Once more, this is a general feature of early Judaism according to most scholars. Leading up to the appearance of the Pharisees in our primary sources, there is an example of King Antiochus IV defiling the altar in the Jerusalem Temple (1 Maccabees 1.54).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The central gathering place for many Palestinian Jews was the Jerusalem Temple. Secondary to this, synagogues (likely "prayer houses") were sacred spaces for local gatherings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear. Our best evidence for artwork and iconography is the third-century CE Dura-Europos synagogue.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: A comment worth adding here is Josephus' comparison to the Stoics in his Life. He does not elaborate, unfortunately.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: An interesting comment in Josephus is that, for the Pharisees, the soul will have the ability to enter into another body in resurrection (scholars refer to this as "transmigration" of the soul).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to Josephus, the Pharisees hold that there is a place of punishment for the wicked and reward for the righteous. The spatial location of these is unclear for the Pharisees in particular.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: Specific protocol for the dead is offered, albeit polemically, in Matthew 23:29-30, referencing decorated tombs and graves. As a sect of early Judaism, Pharisees would have had general protocol for caring for the dead. For example, "burial with one's fathers" (Gen 25:8) was common practice. Specific customs would have varied depending on geographic location (Rome, Egypt, Palestine). From the early Christian literature, we learn that bodies were wrapped in linen according to the "custom of the Jews" (Matt 27:59; John 19:40). It is also important to note that socio-economic factors would have played a role in the degree to which one was carefully shrouded in linen, or if one could afford a "family" or "private" burial site.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: Nothing specific for Pharisees. In later centuries, Jews living in Egypt appear to have practiced mummification according to material evidence. Burial customs could vary depending on geography.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Catacombs, private, or family burials were all options for early Jews during this period (See, for example, Beit she'arim). It is likely the Pharisees utilized these methods, but nothing in particular is available to us in the evidence.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: How, exactly, the corpse was prepared in posture is not provided in the literary evidence. In some archaeological evidence, we find that bodies were laid in particular directions; however, this would be difficult to determine for the Pharisees.

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: How, exactly, the corpse was prepared in posture is not provided in the literary evidence. In some archaeological evidence, we find that bodies were laid in particular directions; however, this would be difficult to determine for the Pharisees.

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: How, exactly, the corpse was prepared in posture is not provided in the literary evidence. In some archaeological evidence, we find that bodies were laid in particular directions; however, this would be difficult to determine for the Pharisees.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are later depictions of Jewish sects washing the deceased in open air, but nothing in particular to Pharisees.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The later literary evidence indicates that the treatment of the deceased in burial customs could be a privilege of the elite. The extent to which one is prepared, the material with which one is buried. This seems plausible for our period, but difficult to determine for target religious group.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One of the difficulties in determining an answer to this is outside of distinct religious indicators (e.g., from inscriptions), it can be difficult to determine the religious affiliation of private grave sites during this period. With that said, Matthew 23:29-30 says that graves are decorated by Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: One can assume a level of formality to burial, but not distinct to Pharisees. Also, socio-economic level could determine the extent to which one was formally prepared for burial.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: In the Torah, God can be described with anthropomorphisms.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: While God is portrayed in the Hebrew Bible with kingly qualities, and may be conflated with monarchs, there is nothing in particular about Pharisees here.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: It is worth noting that one of the issues the Pharisees took up with the Sadducees during the Hasmonean period was the role of the high priest in political affairs.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Notes: Once more, the connection and the role of the High Priest to the ruling class was a divisive issue in late Hellenistic Judaism. During the Roman period, the High Priest is appointed by Rome (e.g., John Hyrcanus II). For more, see E. P. Sanders, *Judaism: Practice and Belief*, 317-340.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Notes: The Pharisees' monotheistic understanding of God largely comports with others forms of early Judaism during this time.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: While there is nothing distinct about the Pharisees here, in Second Temple Judaism God's knowledge is unlimited, in some cases to amass interest from other groups (see The Letter of Aristeas for example).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The assumption is yes. God appoints the High Priest, for example. In distinction from the Sadducees, Josephus describes the Pharisees as subscribing to both "fate" and human action (whereas, the Sadducees remove fate). This would seem to suggest a degree of causal efficacy.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: To clarify "negative" further: The Pharisees would attribute (as would virtually all of early Judaism) anger or wrath to God. However, the Pharisees also placed an emphasis on human action as well, namely that God's wrath was more of a "justice" issue than unbridled rage.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: This is general to early Judaism, and not particular to the Pharisees. Worship of other gods is strictly condemned in the literary sources during this period; however, some evidence may suggest syncretism. (See, for example, Letter of Aristobulus).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Nothing in particular that is unique about the Pharisees here in comparison to other sects of early Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The evidence for everyday life is probable, especially considering the connotations for "walking" in Hebrew Bible, but nothing specific for Pharisee sect. The role of the synagogue in daily life would another factor to consider.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While there is evidence of dreams as a mode of divine communication (Num. 12:6-8; Jer. 23:25-28; Dan. 7:1), we do not have any evidence that includes an experience for the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Prayer and purity (especially eating) rituals are important to Pharisee sect. Early synagogues are referred to with the Greek term *proseuche*, meaning prayer. The debate here is whether or not one should classify prayer as divination.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists, the Pharisees among them, had their place in divine mediation, but only as a form of teaching. Their emphasis on oral tradition does stand out here.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other form of communication with living:

–Yes [specify]: For the Pharisees, the Hebrew Scriptures, and the tradition of the elders (Oral tradition) would have been instrumental in understanding God's voice in the community.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unclear. Theoretically, if the soul is immortal (unlike the Sadducees) one could imagine a belief in human spirits.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The presence of angels as divine "messengers" or mediators of God's revelation is certainly present in the Hebrew Bible. To what extent the Pharisees specifically adhere to a type of angelology is unclear from the evidence. Pharisees do appear to have a belief in demons and "the prince of demons" (Matthew 9:34).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The evidence is unclear. According to the Gospel of Matthew, the manifestation of demons within humans can be seen (Matthew 9:34).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: See, once more, Matthew 9:27-34 for an example.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is hard to provide a clear answer for Pharisees, other than the dispute they have with Jesus in the Gospels regarding the "prince of demons" (See Matthew 9:34). In early Judaism and Christianity more broadly, the answer would be "yes" depending on the literary text one reads.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We simply do not have evidence for this for the Pharisees. If reward was mediated by an angel, it would ultimately derive from God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From the activity of demons in the Gospels, and those specifically witnessed by the Pharisees (as in Matthew 9:32-34), the implication is that the demons are harming (not punishing) humans.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Our knowledge of the activity of angels and demons in Second Temple Judaism is highly mythologized in places. Furthermore, we do not have accounts for the Pharisees in this regard.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Our knowledge of the activity of angels and demons in Second Temple Judaism

is highly mythologized in places. Furthermore, we do not have accounts for the Pharisees in this regard.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From the evidence for Pharisees, it would appear that demons have the ability to possess human bodies. However, the degree to which they believed anything else about demons (such as the Prince of Demons) is unclear.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is possible for the Pharisees. There are examples of this in early Judaism, especially in apocalyptic literature. In the Testament of Abraham, for example, Abraham, guided by an angel/messenger, appears to survey or "monitor" the world, including very private activities.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done only by high god:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Josephus tells us that according to the Pharisees an eternal punishment awaits evil people (Ant. 18.1.3); however, he does not specify further. Elsewhere, Josephus says the Pharisees believe in fate while the Sadducees "take away fate" (Ant 13.5.9). We are to infer from context that God is the one who ultimately enacts or allows divine punishment. In some cases in early Judaism, it is God alone who enacts punishment, in other cases, it is demons or other worldly beings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Josephus tells us that according to the Pharisees an eternal punishment awaits evil people (Ant. 18.1.3); however, he does not specify further. Elsewhere, Josephus says the Pharisees believe in fate while the Sadducees "take away fate" (Ant 13.5.9). We are to infer from context that God is the one who ultimately enacts or allows divine punishment. In some cases in early Judaism, it is God alone who enacts punishment, in other cases, it is demons or other worldly beings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This question is worth considering further. The information we have is vague, but Josephus states: The Pharisees "do not take away the freedom from men of acting as they think fit: since their notion is, that it hath pleased God to make a temperament" (Ant. 18.1.3; see also Ant. 13.5.9). In other words, it would be plausible that one's demise is caused because of one's own foolish actions. Strictly speaking, this

characterization of human action (i.e., without fate) is more indicative of the Sadducees according to Josephus.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Once more, from the little context we have, it is difficult to determine with confidence for the Pharisees. Human punishment, on the other hand, is enacted due to boundary or ritual violations.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, with a caveat here. The assumption is that threat of punishment would likely enforce group norms. According to Josephus and in turn his account of the Pharisees, divine punishment is strictly enacted upon the "souls of bad men" (Josephus, War 2.8.14). When the Pharisees suggest a lenient punishment, John Hyrcanus becomes "very angry" (Ant. 13.10.6).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to be specific here. Because divine punishment in our literary record is recorded as final, it would not be understood to correct bad behavior. Although one could say to the contrary that the threat of divine punishment could correct bad behavior.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: From Josephus, we know that the Sadducees placed considerable emphasis on human action, while the Pharisees seemed to account for "fate" (i.e., God). However, it is important to note that when Josephus speaks of the Pharisees on punishment, he makes an effort to suggest that they were not severe in enacting it (Ant. 13.10.6).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: It is difficult to determine from the evidence, but the answer is likely "no." According to Josephus's account, the Pharisees were not interested in severe punishment. While he delineates that "bad souls" go to a place of torment, he does not tell us the degree to which it was emphasized.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: Described as an "everlasting prison" (Josephus, Ant. 18.1.3).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The level of punishment is not offered in detail. It is described as an "everlasting prison" and as "punishment" (Josephus, Ant. 18.1.3).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This seems plausible. Our literary evidence suggests the afterlife, but it is hard to imagine (especially with the broader context of early Judaism) that political affairs would not be interpreted through this lens as well. See especially Ant. 13.10.6.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: According to Josephus' account of the Pharisees the reward is given for living virtuously. One has the "power to revive and live again." The implication from context (and other literary sources within Second Temple Judaism) is the God gives these rewards.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As stated above, this question is worth considering further. The information we have is vague, but Josephus states: The Pharisees "do not take away the freedom from men of acting as they think fit: since their notion is, that it hath pleased God to make a temperament" (Ant. 18.1.3; see also Ant. 13.5.9). In other words, it would be plausible that one's reward is caused because of one's good actions; however, this is more of a feature of the Sadducees. Additionally, Josephus's mention of fate in connection with the Pharisees may suggest a degree of impersonal cause and effect.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Hard to say with confidence. In theory, the promise of reward by God would return devotion from the adherent (e.g., prayer), but it is not clear if this is the purpose of divine reward.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The answer would likely be yes here. The moral boundaries by which the Pharisees were governed would be enforced by the promise of resurrection.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Josephus offers an account of the punitive verdict rendered by Pharisees upon Eleazar. In this context, however, the notion is not divine punishment. (Ant. 13.10.6).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear if this is "highly emphasized." A distinction of the Pharisee sect, however, is the promise of resurrection to the righteous. (cf. the Sadducees in Mark 12:18-27).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Our literary evidence does not indicate the degree of sensory pleasure one might experience in the afterlife. More of an absence of the alternative (punishment).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From Second Temple Judaism, the answer is likely yes. However, for the Pharisees, our literary evidence does not indicate the degree of sensory pleasure one might experience in the afterlife. More of an absence of the alternative (punishment).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: From Second Temple Judaism, the answer is likely yes. However, for the Pharisees, our literary evidence does not indicate the degree to which one might experience happiness in the afterlife.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It would depend on how one interprets the transmigration of the soul as illustrated in Josephus. If one's soul leaves the body to enter into another body, this would not be properly "reincarnation" but there are some similarities here.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees, distinct from the Sadducees, believe in resurrection of the dead as a reward for the righteous.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is difficult to determine. It seems likely that political affairs would receive divine interpretation (Josephus's entire project might suggest this), but we do not have specific indications that divine reward is for the present life.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Gospel of Matthew has the Pharisees ask Jesus specifically about "the Messiah" (22:41). One could argue from this evidence, that there is an awareness of the belief about messianism, and not that it is espoused by the Pharisees. Traditionally, messianism in early Judaism has been associated with portions of the Dead Sea Scrolls and the New Testament. However, with great dispute, some have assigned Pharisaic authorship to the Psalms of Solomon (see esp. chapter 17). This seems unlikely. For more, see John J. Collins, *The Scepter and the Star: The Messiahs of the Dead Sea Scrolls and other Ancient Literature* (New York: Doubleday, 1995).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The degree to which the conventional/moral distinction is present is hard to say. One of the defining features of the sect of the Pharisees appears to be purity regulations. Eating with unwashed hands as a "tradition of the elders," for example, causes a bit of a stir in the Gospel sources (Matthew 15:1-20).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In contrast to some of our evidence for the Essenes.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer here is most likely, "yes," within the broader scope of Second Temple Judaism; however, our evidence for the Pharisees in particular is limited (in contrast to the Essenes, for example). The emphasis on purity rituals in our literature largely revolves around eating customs for Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 9:14-17 indicates that fasting is a typical feature of ritual practices among the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: The answer is yes, depending how one interprets the Pharisees "despise delicacies in diet." (Josephus, Ant. 18.1.3) More broadly, one could cite eating restrictions in the Hebrew Bible and early Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Presumably, one would have already been circumcised before studying with the Pharisees. Therefore, this would not be a membership requirement in this sense.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The Pharisees appeared to place an emphasis on prayer, divine worship, and sacrifices (see, e.g., Josephus, Ant. 18.1.3; Matthew 6:5-15).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: According to Josephus' account, the Pharisees emphasize both fate and human action, so that human beings may act virtuously.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: There are periods when the Pharisees are stigmatized, especially by the Sadducees. Because they appear to control the populace, this generates conflict from other sects.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Eating rituals as well as prayer would have been practiced in private.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: If we are considering the "sacrifices" Josephus speaks of in regard to the Pharisees, then one could assume that the type of sacrifice would have been regulated by a priest. He says "they perform them according to their direction" (Ant. 18.1.3).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The incident in the Synoptic Gospels regarding hand-washing appears to be an issue of orthopraxy and "the tradition of the elders." (See Mark 7:1-23; Matthew 15:1-20)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is difficult to say in regard to the Pharisees. One could assume that synagogue

attendance was synchronic, and thus there were occasions where prayer or Scripture reading was synchronic, from other sources within Second Temple Judaism.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: But only as a feature common to early Judaism, not the Pharisees in particular.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Hair:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dress:

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 23:5 states "They make their phylacteries wide and the tassels on their garments long."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The indication in Second Temple Judaism is that several forms of Judaism did employ fictive kinship terminology (including early Christians). For example, the designation of "children" for the people of Israel and "Father" for God could indicate fictive kinship. However, we cannot say for certain if this applied to the Pharisees. Josephus is sympathetic to the Pharisees and Paul is a former Pharisee, so one could infer a measure of fictive kinship from either of these two authors.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: During the Roman period, Judea became a Roman province, before which Jews enjoyed a degree of autonomy and self-governance under the High Priest at the Jerusalem Temple. During this period, the role of the High Priest and his connections to the Seleucid Empire (and later Romans) became a source of inter/intra religious conflict. It is also worth mentioning that early Jews had a governing body (gerousia) within the state, which appears to have functioned autonomously prior to Roman rule. For more, see Mary Smallwood, *The Jews Under Roman Rule: From Pompey to Diocletian, A Study in Political Relations* (Leiden: Brill, 1981).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Notes: The Pharisees in particular would not have possessed an institutionalized famine relief outside of sharing common meals and the Temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to Josephus, when famine struck in Judea and Syria, Herod offered charitable assistance (See Ant. 15.9). In another case, Queen Helena, who purportedly worshipped at the Jerusalem temple provided famine relief (Ant. 20.2.5).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: The Hebrew Bible clearly advocates care for the poor (Jer 20:13; Amos 2:6); however, it does not seem to be until the Rabbinic period that we see organized charity programs. See Pieter W. van der Horst, "Organized Charity in the Ancient World: Pagan, Jewish, Christian," pp. 116-33 in *Jewish and Christian Communal Identities in the Roman World* (ed. Yair Furstenberg; AJEC 94; Boston: Brill, 2016).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It would be difficult to demonstrate an "institutionalized" form of care and even more so, among Pharisees specifically. However, one could show from the context of Second Temple Judaism more broadly that family care was important even mandated in certain cases.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: It appears from at least Josephus's autobiography that Pharisees were a group with which one studied.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: Our evidence indicates male participation.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The short answer is yes. As in the case of Josephus or the narrative anecdote we receive about John Hyrcanus' friend Jonathan, one could learn from the Pharisees, become one of them, or leave. Presumably, nothing is preventing an upperclass person, such as Josephus, from education by other means. (He even compares them to the Stoics in his Life.)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It does not seem to be the case that Pharisees had a formal bureaucracy up and running within their own ranks. The notion of the "tradition of the elders" indicates an authoritative structure, but not necessarily a bureaucratic one.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Especially in the case of Queen Alexandra, it appears that the Pharisees have some degree of influential according to Josephus (see War 1.5; "And now the Pharisees joined themselves to her, to assist her in the government").

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The degree to which a Pharisee would have access to public food storage would be difficult to determine. Under the reign of Queen Alexandra, it is possible Pharisees had more access to government resources, but this does not mean it was "public."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In the first-century in Judea (as a province of Rome), the water management would be controlled by the government.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Presumably yes. Judaism functioned freely as a legal religion under Roman rule until Emperor Nero and the destruction of the Temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Matthew 23:23 indicates a tenth of one's goods ("mint, dill, cumin" were given) likely in support of the Levites and the Temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This appears to be the case in the early Christian literature. In Matthew 22:15-22, the dialogue

between the Pharisees and Jesus confirms a tax by Caesar.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Consider this passage from John Hyrcanus' interaction with the Pharisees as recorded by Josephus (Ant. 13.10.6; trans. Whiston): He told Hyrcanus, that "Eleazar had cast such a reproach upon him according to the common sentiments of all the Pharisees: and that this would be made manifest if he would but ask them the question, what punishment they thought this man deserved? For that he might depend upon it, that the reproach was not laid on him with their approbation; if they were for punishing him as his crime deserved." So the Pharisees made answer, that "He deserved stripes and bonds: but that it did not seem right to punish reproaches with death." And indeed the Pharisees, even upon other occasions, are not apt to be severe in punishments."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: Not "judges" per se, but judgments. Consider the same passage quoted above (Ant. 13.10.6; trans. Whiston): "So the Pharisees made answer, that "He deserved stripes and bonds: but that it did not seem right to punish reproaches with death." And indeed the Pharisees, even upon other occasions, are not apt to be severe in punishments."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Once more, the Pharisees appear closely associated with Queen Alexandra for a period of time. The extent to which they interacted or offered advice upon judicial matters is unclear. Consider the passage in Josephus, War 1.5: "But these Pharisees artfully insinuated themselves into her favour by little and little, and became themselves the real administrators of the public affairs: they banished and reduced whom they pleased"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Notes: Josephus is clear that the Pharisees thought death too harsh.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Under Salome Alexandra, "[the Pharisees] banished and reduced whom they pleased."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: In the passage already referenced at John Hyrcanus' banquet, corporal punishment is recommended.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: Not formally mentioned as such.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The practice of Corban, which appears in the Gospel of Mark, is worth mentioning here (see Mark 7:11-13). The extent to which Corban was invoked to protect one's own property from the Temple is unclear. It does not seem to be a punitive practice.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This is difficult to answer with confidence in regard to the Pharisees. They certainly fall out of favor with John Hyrcanus, and would also be subject to the Roman government as residents of Judea in the first-century.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Outside of the legal code within Torah, what we know about Pharisees from early Christian literature includes narrative episodes depicting disputes about the "tradition of the elders."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As recorded in Josephus' Jewish War, we are aware of Jewish participants in the Jewish revolt, including the Sicarii. The connection between the Sicarii and Pharisees is difficult to determine.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Josephus presents the Pharisees in a favorable light in his writings; however, they do seem to disappear following the destruction of the Temple. From the conflict that ensues around 70 CE, it is hard to imagine that the Roman military is working to "protect" Pharisees, in so far as subject them to Roman rule.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: No semitic dialects unique to the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: Josephus is the most obvious example here. He has access to both Greco-Roman education and the "philosophy" of the Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— No

Notes: There is evidence among the Dead Scrolls of sectarian calendars at Qumran, but nothing directly tied to Pharisees.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Notes: From the evidence we have on tithing one's "mint, dill, cumin," it is possible that Pharisees participated in small scale agriculture. Because they are situated in the late Hellenistic to early Roman period, other forms of commerce, especially in the agora, would have been accessible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Because Pharisees are situated in the late Hellenistic to early Roman period, other

forms of commerce, especially in the agora, would have been accessible.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

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